

Exploring the Multiculturalism in Indian Writings

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Abstract

India is home to several literary languages that are among the most advanced in the world. Both languages have rich histories of literature. Since the Indian Constitution recognizes English as an "official language," it is presumed to be the primary literary language. Indian literature's multiculturalism stands apart from other examples of postcolonial English writing. This Paper's Primary Goal is to examine Multiculturalism's Function in Indian English Literature. A person of Indian ancestry will always be bilingual and likely fluent in many other languages. He has the innate ability to adapt his cultural code to the demands of his surroundings. He also maintains a natural, indigenous social structure. The words "Marga" and "Desi" were often employed in Indian languages to institutionalize these various pulls. A distinct Indian English style is impossible to achieve in India. As a metaphor, contemporary Indian culture might be considered a person is wearing a pair of medieval garb, antique shoes, and contemporary headgear. We might expect multiculturalism to provide literature with fresh vitality if we read widely.

Keywords: Multiculturalism, Ethnic Diversity, Contribution, Recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

This cultural phenomenon of English's centrality to Indian literature is intriguing, given that English is not an Indian language. English is the primary language spoken in these countries, as well as in Australia, Canada, and the United States. India is home to several literary languages that are among the most advanced in the world. Literature in these languages dates back many years. International students sometimes mistakenly believe India has no literature in languages other than English. Since the Indian Constitution designates English as an "official language," it is generally accepted that English is the primary literary language in India. Indian literature written in English is the most recent literary genre to flourish in India. Writing in English is challenging for Indians since it forces them to choose between their language and English, "this other tongue which has been our close adversary throughout the previous two centuries" [1].

In 1835, Lord Macaulay pushed for English to be a teaching medium in India's schools. The British colonial government in India regarded it as a way to educate and modernize the indigenous population. Since English literature was produced in the country of the rulers and

was praised by them, it immediately acquired a high cultural status in India when it was introduced to school and university curricula. India already had a long and rich tradition of literature when this encounter occurred, with works written in more than a dozen living languages. Traditional Indian art and literature have always been very varied. Over time, it has absorbed many other cultures. The English word "culture" lacks the lexical breadth to describe India's cultural milieu adequately. The word refers to the defining characteristics of a particular social group. The terms "Elite culture" and "Middle-class culture" do an excellent job of describing the actual types of cultures that exist.

There are crucial distinctions between discussing multiculturalism in Indian literature and discussing it in other postcolonial literature written in English. It is almost hard to fit India's dizzying array of distinct subcultures into a single sociological, linguistic or ethnic cultural structure model, given the interplay between India's many different social, linguistic, racial, and religious traditions. A basic multicultural setting should not be compared to a complicated one. Instead, it's meant to compare very intricate and intricately complex settings. Such complexities are unavoidable in a civilization where the spoken language is one of almost 80, the written literary language is one of nearly 20 languages, and there have been mass migrations of the population once every 3000 years. About a hundred years ago, English became the primary medium for disseminating Indian literature. However, multiculturalism is one of the oldest and most enduring aspects of Indian culture [2].

An Indian, on the other hand, is always going to be bilingual and will always be immersed in a culture with more than two languages. He has the innate ability to adapt his cultural code to the demands of his surroundings. Even he is a part of a natural and indigenous social setting rich with various cultural norms and practices. The Indian languages' traditional words for these various attractions, Marga and Desi, respectively, are both rooted in the traditions of their respective countries. Marga refers to the cultures that permeate the whole subcontinent in a horizontal sense, whereas Desi refers to the vertical, local, and rapidly changing aspects of one's cultural identity. Historically, economic shifts, religious norms, and shared linguistics have contributed to increased social mobility. Perhaps the marga traditions, the foreign traditions, and the desi traditions can be seen as forming a tripartite connection to explain the complex social fragmentation and development we see. Traditions practiced by foreigners in India were inspired by Marga culture and Desi's ways of life. These were simultaneously stylized, formalized, and elevated to preeminent status in Indian culture. Also, like the customs of the desi kinds, it was put to use in a practical, down-to-earth manner that was in close harmony with daily experience. Indian authors writing in English have adopted a schizophrenic persona that is both stylized and practical [3].

As a result, the English-language works of Indian authors face challenges exclusive to this subgenre and not shared by any other authors from the Commonwealth. The first is that it has developed several identities. There is a presumption that the mainstream is better than anything else. By mimicking both, foreign cultures in India feel pressured to adopt a more unified, pan-Indian identity while yet retaining the richness and color of its indigenous roots. You may see

this tendency in the English-language writing styles originating from India. Some authors, like R.K. Narayan and Mulk Raj Anand, have been publishing for almost fifty years, yet they still have to translate regional notions and terminology into standard English. Dialect writers in England and South America both confront the same challenge. Just because an Indian writer is bilingual or bicultural does not mean they must write in two tones or use text neutrality or colorization. The non-typical Indian authors, such as V.S. Naipaul and Salman Rushdie, are also bicultural, but they have developed a whole different style as a result of avoiding the cultural conflict that plagues the average Indian author. This discord necessitates a heightened focus on the characters' uses of sarcasm, wit, myth, rhetoric, and other linguistic traits.

Compared to local tongues, English is highly esteemed in India. While the Indian author may have a sense of ownership over this "Indian" language, he is writing for an audience that shares his socioeconomic background. This discord prevents the Indian English language from developing into a coherent discourse. English literature in India faces a second, more significant issue due to rising cultural tensions. The Indian country has embraced English as one of its two official languages, the other being Hindi. But although Hindi is a regional language with a distinct geographical foundation, English does not.

Consequently, it serves dual purposes as a language of rank and permanence. Because it is an international language, it is known as a status language and not an Indian language, and it is more studied than spoken in India. Hence it is a static language. It enjoys an incredibly resourceful language that it has been elsewhere. The apparent results of this approach to stay in with the worldwide status of the language, most authors acquire a studied sarcastic tone at the same time; to relieve it of its static, load it with excessive local color. The ambiguity that permeates "Nissim Eziqel's poetry," which faithfully reproduces a style of English that is somewhat humorous and authentically Indian, is illustrative of these views. The other is the epic "Savitri" by Aurobindo, which uses Miltonic language and is rich with allusions to old, stylized folklore. Thus, English is recognized in India as a national language, although it is utilized primarily as a global language to express India's unique culture. Moreover, like other cultural institutions in India, it bears the weight of the complicated triangle formed by the marga, the foreign, and the desi.

This threefold cultural connection is readily apparent in the works of many authors, especially those who engage in reflective practices. R. Partha Sarathy's "Rough Passage" is a poetic expression of this connection. The poem is broken up into Exile, Trail, and Homecoming. In the first part, he finds out he is Indian and is shocked by the British foreign environment. The poem's language and the intensity of feeling in this passage are on par with the western canon for alienation. The second part focuses on the poet's travels and relationships, while the third and fourth parts detail his maturation as a person due to philosophical disappointments. The poet considers western, Marga, and Desi perspectives on the theme together. From this vantage point, Sri Aurobindo's "Savitri" and Jayanta Mahapatra's "Relationship" are the other two critical poems in Indian English literature. Therefore, the use of English as a medium of creative writing in India not only broadens the writer's canvas but also dilutes his colors. An

early example of Indian literature in English may be found in R.K. Narayan's "The painter of signs" or "The Talkative man" [4].

Such a destiny appears to have been etched into the very DNA of Indian English writing from the time it was born, with its long and complicated history of confrontation and cooperation between western, Marga, and Desi cultural traditions. In a nutshell, Indian authors had learned how to write in other languages even before the arrival of the English language in India. Indian authors used alien languages like Arabic and Persian. Many authors have written in languages other than their native tongue; for example, the 13th-century Persian poet Amir Khosrau and the Sanskrit poet Jagannath pandit are only two instances. Indian intellectuals nowadays are not outraged by the fact that English literature is taught in schools throughout the country. Some British ideologists, influenced by Sir William Jones, including the thinker Raja Ram Mohan Roy, pushed for instruction in the traditional languages of Arabic and Sanskrit. What is now known as the "Anglicist vs. Orientalist" argument?

On the other hand, there existed a tension between western and Marga traditions. These languages, such as Gujarati, Tamil, and Marathi, have longstanding literary canons. As far as I could tell, they were all Desi customs. The British government in India eventually settled the argument by deciding to include all three elements in the country's educational system. The Indian government still recognizes three languages as official. This strategy has been in place continuously since 1835, and as a result, all three cultural streams are still included in the English writings of Indians.

Four distinct writing modes emerge from India's heterogeneous literary milieu in English literature:

- Aesthetic in which exotic cultural elements are woven into a cohesive whole with marga cultural elements. Raja Rao is the literary embodiment of this concept since he mixes a universal existentialist with a very Indian kind of sentimentality.
- A fusion of local or discultural elements with nationalism or the Marga culture. The day of the Turban, by Prathap Sarma, is an excellent example of a Punjab-themed book.
- Marga traits where sarcasm and sentimentality continuously obstruct one other; • International cultural aspects collide with national or marga features. This is the typical fashion for Mulk Raj Anand.
- A fusion of national and regional, marga and desi, cultural influences. In some instances, R.K. Narayan seems to be struggling with this issue.

Examples of the four categories of poets may be seen in the works of A.K.Ramanujan, Jayantha Mahapatra, Sri Aurobindo, and R. Partha Sarathy. On this basis, one can argue that an indigenous Indian variety of English is impossible in India. The multicultural setting in which Indian English literature is written directly affects the literary styles that appear within it. Modern India's potential for solid creativity lies in the collision of these three cultural currents. The English language and the foreign culture it encapsulates are pretty young, dating back just

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a century or two. Around the turn of the twentieth century, a new cultural identity evolved in India; this identity, known as "desi," absorbed and preserved the societal imprints of ages before. Even older than the rise of Indian civilization are the marga traditions. Thus, the agricultural society, the feudal society, and the industrialized society are the cradles of these three distinct civilizations. As a metaphor, contemporary Indian culture might be considered a person is wearing a pair of medieval garb, antique shoes, and contemporary headgear. The Indian sensibility places a high value on the very old, even when it is useless, and on the new, even when it is immature, further compounding the issue. As a result, respect is shown for both Sanskrit and the culture that developed around it and English and the culture that developed around it. Such perspectives on language and culture may be traced back to the Indian concept of the tradition known as Parampara. The cultural memory of India has retained the past of its many similar languages. Indians, in particular, have a remarkable capacity for picking up the lingo of those from other cultures. However, these second languages are always considered fundamentally different and only partially integrated. India's literary output is slowly but steadily becoming more traditional.

Similarly, the English-language canon of Indian literature has its roots in the colonial period. One of the most significant effects of colonialism on Indian culture was the rise of a revivalist movement. However, the colonial rule also sparked an increased desire to copy the British. An overwhelming reverence for India's distant past may be traced back to the revivalist fervor generated by the Indological awe of ancient Indian civilization. The need to copy it led to unhealthy respect for the English language. Sociologists use the words "Sanskritization" and "westernization" to characterize these two movements. These two tendencies are now deeply embedded in contemporary Indian literature and culture. Severe abnormalities, including gaps in the tradition's self-awareness, are generated as a result of this process, and the development of the tradition itself becomes arduous.

A. Culture

A quote from Benjamin Alire Sáenz's *I Wants to Write an American Poem II* (2004) reads, "I cling to my culture because it is my skin because it is my heart because it is my voice because it breathes my mother's mother's mother into me... I am blind without the glasses of my culture" (253) [5]. The discourse on culture is not a new phenomenon in social sciences, anthropology, history, psychology, and humanities. It has been integrated profoundly into a postmodern academic circle. Wrangling over the re-conceptualization of the term 'culture' among anthropologists, sociologists, humanists, philosophers, writers, and linguists has become a daily intellectual exercise. "Even Raymond Williams accepts that —Culture is one of the two or three most complicated words in the English language (87) [6]". However, the aura of culture has not diminished even in the globalized digital age. Lauren Harvey said metaphorically, —Culture is for man what water is for fish and air is for bird (84) [7]. Indeed, Culture is an amorphous but fascinating, challenging but stimulating, and ancient but fashionable term for all. It synthesizes different meanings, perspectives, arguments, and applications for different people.

Etymologically, the idea of culture has been derived from the agricultural process of cultivating the land. It finds its roots in Latin 'cultura' meaning 'a cultivating agriculture'. It was the Ancient Roman orator Cicero who used the term culture for the first time in his *Tusculanae Disputationes*, where he talked about 'cultural animi' (the cultivation of the soul). The non-agricultural use of the term "culture" reappeared in modern Europe during the writing of the 18th-century German thinkers. In German intellectual tradition, culture is perceived in a different and particular sense. German 'Kultur' referred exclusively to the levels of excellence in fine arts, literature, music, and individual perfection (Velkley 3) [8]. Chris Jenks, in his book *Culture* (1993), averred that the idea of culture emerged in the late eighteenth or into the nineteenth century as a reaction and outcome of massive changes in the structure and quality of social, political, and personal life through industrialization, urbanization, improved system of communication and technology. It was the period when people experienced unprecedented transformations in their life. (Jenks 7) [9] In the Sanskrit language, the word 'Samskruti' is used as an equivalent word for culture. Sam means 'very well,' and Krtam means—that which is done.

Therefore Samskruti means—that which is very well done or made or very well refined. Swami Tejomayananda has proposed two essential points to understand the true nature of culture- first is Prakruti which means nature, and second is Vikruti, meaning perversion. He states that Prakruti is an inherent penchant in human beings and animals. Desires like hunger, thirst, and sleep are natural to all. When we feel hungry, we go in search of food. Thus, we act by nature; it is called Prakruti. As long as the action of animals and human beings are according to nature, there is no problem. However, when desires and actions grow out of proportion and become uncontrollable, it is called Vikruti. For instance, if one feels tired, he sleeps for some time to refresh. Here sleep is not the problem. However, if he sleeps fourteen or sixteen hours a day, something is erroneous there. It is not natural. It is Vikruti. Animals are always faithful to their Prakruti, but human beings are not.

B. Multiculturalism

Due to the rise of multiculturalism, diverse cultural minorities are in the position to enjoy equal rights along with the majority culture. However, as there are advocates of multiculturalism, there are also a few critics who are not in favor of multiculturalism. Some critics shun the idea of multiculturalism and label it as a failure. They argued that the nations recognized with their distinct cultural identity are now losing that identity due to enforced multiculturalism. The validity and criticism of multiculturalism are discussed further in the present chapter. Presently, it is essential to begin with the definition of the phenomenon of multiculturalism. In short, multiculturalism means the coexistence of multiple diverse cultures and their sub-varieties within a single society. It means the acceptance of cultural, religious, racial, and ethnic diversity. "Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary (2005) defines multiculturalism as the practice of giving importance to all cultures in a society, and including people of different races, religions, languages, and traditions. Andrew Heywood defines multiculturalism as—a positive endorsement, even celebration, of communal diversity typically based on either the

right of different groups to respect and recognition or to the alleged benefits to the larger society of moral and cultural diversity (Heywood 314) [10].” Multiculturalism aims to create a harmonious, robust, integrated, and cohesive society. In the western world, multiculturalism often denotes the acceptance of immigrants who form ethnic, racial, religious, cultural, and linguistic minority groups. To protect and preserve the culture and cultural rights of these minority groups, the western world has adopted the policy of multiculturalism. In his seminal work *Rethinking Multiculturalism: Cultural Diversity and Political Theory*, multiculturalist advocate Bhikhu Parekh offers some foundational thoughts on the topic (2000). He argues that multiculturalism is best understood as a worldview rather than a set of policies or a philosophical school with a particular take on man's role in the universe. Three ideas, in his view, form the foundation of multiculturalism. 1) People's ingrained cultural practices 2) The need and value for a diverse cultural landscape #3) the multicultural and pluralistic foundations of all cultures. First, when he talks about how humans are "culturally entrenched," he means that people are brought up in a culturally organized environment and learn to make sense of the world and their relationships with others through the lens of a culturally determined set of values and norms. Second, he means that various cultures stand for distinct meaning systems and perspectives on the ideal life when he says that cultural diversity is both inevitable and desirable. He thinks that people from different backgrounds only partially understand human potential and feelings. Therefore, each civilization needs exposure to other cultures in order to better "understand itself," "extend its intellectual and moral vision," "stretch its imagination," "rescue it from egotism," and "guard against the apparent urge to absolutize oneself." Thirdly, he implies that every culture is intrinsically multiple and reflects a continual interaction between its many traditions and streams of thinking by referring to what he calls the "plural and multicultural structure of each culture" (Parekh 336-38) [11]. From Parekh's vantage point, it is easy to see that people are deeply rooted in various civilizations.

Similar to Postmodernism, Multiculturalism is firmly founded on core beliefs. Multiculturalism is a critical component of the postmodern era. According to Terence Turner's *Anthropology and Multiculturalism* (1993), multiculturalism is the postmodernist response to the delegitimization of the state and the decline of the dominant culture in prosperous Western nations (Turner 416) [12]. In other words, multiculturalism challenges what Gramsci termed it as 'Cultural Hegemony'. Post-modernism saw the cultural hegemony of the western world over the third world. During the colonized period, the first world considered their culture superior and the third world inferior and worthless. The western attitude towards the orient can be seen in Macaulay's notorious comment —a single shelf of a sound European library was worth the whole native literature of India and Arabia (Duiker and Spielvogel 583). “Edward Said termed it as 'Orientalism'. By orientalism, he means —a Western style for dominating, restructuring and having authority over the orient (Said 3).” It is a way of perspective that imagines, emphasizes, exaggerates and distorts differences between Eastern and Western cultures. Orientalism looks at the Eastern culture (the orient) as exotic, backward, uncivilized, and at times dangerous. The western culture established a cultural Hegemony over the eastern culture through orientalism. Multiculturalism shattered the myth of cultural hegemony in the twentieth

century. It established the view that even the minority culture has rights and privileges, which should be respected by the majority culture.

II. INDIA: A MULTICULTURAL NATION

India is a vast multi-cultural, multi-religious, multi-racial, multi-ethnic, and multi-linguistic country and Indian multiculturalism is more than a struggle of immigrants or a theory of minority rights. In fact, in India, there has not been a problem with immigration as compared to that in European countries. On the contrary, Indian multiculturalism forms a complex mosaic of cultures and sub-cultures encompassing many religions, castes, creeds, sects, classes, races, and ethnic groups. Scholars often ask how India, in a state of poverty, illiteracy, economic depravity, overloaded population, and extreme regionalism, has survived until now and not broken into pieces. The answer could be found in the words of our first Prime Minister of India, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru who described India as a nation with —unity in diversity— the very phrase goes close to the notion of multiculturalism. Even Tariq Modood [13], a proponent of multiculturalism, acknowledges Indian multiculturalism by stating:

...some contemporary societies are much more deeply multicultural than other societies.... The former includes countries like India, which has many millions of followers of most of the major world religions, as well as being the home of many smaller-sized religions, dozens of ethnic groups, over twenty official languages, and so on. (Modood 5)

For India, multiculturalism is not a new doctrine. It has existed in Indian society since the time unknown in the form of individuals. Even the great Indian epics Ramayana and Mahabharata reflect the ideology of multiculturalism. Mahaveer and Buddha also preached and inculcated the ideologies and values among their disciples, which tell the people to embrace all with love. Emperor Asoka, Mogul Emperor Akbar, and the great King Chattrapati Shivaji implemented equality policy in their kingdoms.

Moreover, during the colonized period, Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Jyotiba Phule, Mahatma Gandhi, and Dr. B. R. Ambedkar launched a movement for social reformation in India. These people challenged the rigid social structure in contemporary India. Phule openly criticized the dominant Brahmin people for their ill-treatment of the deprived section of society. Mahatma Gandhi, throughout his life, attempted to remove the crisis between the Hindus and the Muslims to promote cultural exchange. He called downtrodden, outcastes, and untouchables Harijan, which means —People of the God. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar is a messiah for untouchables and downtrodden who struggled for their right to equality and won the battle. _Unity in diversity is the soul of Indian multiculturalism. It can be found in religions, regions, languages, and societies. Religiously, India comprises almost all religions of the world as Hindu, Islam, Sikh, Buddhist, Jain, Jew, Christians, etc. Each of these religions has its internal structure consisting of various sects, sub-sects, creeds, sub-creeds, sects, and so on. Hindus, for instance, have Shaiva, Vaishnav, Mahanubhav, and Varkari sects. Islam has Shiya, Sunni, Sufi, etc. Every religion can practice its philosophy and rites, rituals, beliefs, customs, and festivities in

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a civilized manner. Besides, India is structured with gross regional divisions based on languages. The people in each region feel proud of their regional culture. Gujarati, Maharashtrian, Kashmiri, Punjabi, Rajsthani, North-east culture, and Kannada represent their own culture, representing their region and language. Linguistically, Indian people use more than 1600 different languages and dialects. The Indian constitution recognizes 22 languages. Besides, Indians are bilingual, trilingual, or multilingual while operating in various walks of life.

India's rich past, breathtaking landscape, and varied population have all left their mark on its unique culture. Religions, dialects, dance, music, architecture, clothing, culinary habits, and traditions all have regional variants throughout India, yet they all have a similar thread. India's culture is a synthesis of the many local traditions practiced throughout the country. In India, societal constraints and stratification are manifested in the rigorous phenomena of caste. The people in India belonging to different castes, creeds, sects, religions, communities, races, and genders form the unique phenomenon known as the 'Indian'. Though they represent oneness in the context of national culture, they still assert their identities through their customs and values, traditions and precepts; cultures and religions; and lifestyles and habits. Ironically, it is difficult to find out an Indian in India.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Since the origin of the term 'Multiculturalism', there has been a temptation and fascination about it among scholars, critics, socialists, political pundits, educationalists, etc. Multiculturalism as a state policy was adopted and implemented first by Canada, then followed by USA, UK, and Australia during the 1970s. Since the 1990s, western scholars like Will Kymlicka [14], William Galston, Charles Taylor, Bhikhu Parekh, Anne Phillip, Tariq Modood, Brian Barry, Susan Okin, Simon Thompson, Oliver Christl started to pen their views and observations about multiculturalism in their works. Their works and views collectively aid in developing the critical socio-political theory of multiculturalism.

According to Bikhu Parekh (2000) [11], it was Will Kymlicka who "first dealt with the topic of Liberal responses to cultural diversity" in his book *Liberalism, Community and Culture* (1989), so laying the groundwork for debate on the notion of multiculturalism. *Multicultural Citizenship: A Liberal Theory of Minority Rights* (1995) is his most recent work addressing this issue (99). He was a multiculturalist from the liberal school of thought. This book is where Kymlicaka develops his novel idea of the rights and status of minority cultures, arguing that minorities do, in fact, have 'collective rights that are compatible with liberal democratic norms and the typical liberal objections to recognizing such rights. Principles of liberty, fairness, and patriotism form their foundation. Kymlicka argues that the needs and ambitions of immigrants are different from those of indigenous people and national minorities. Hence there is no universal formula that can be applied to all groups in regard to their rights. Central to any understanding of multicultural politics is the topics he covers, such as language rights, ethnic representation, religious education, federalism, and secession.

Another recent work of his, *The Politics of Reconciliation in Multicultural Societies* (2008), argues that two significant parallel intellectual and political movements have emerged to meet the challenge of the 'politics of reconciliation' by recognizing and empowering minorities in multicultural societies. The politics of difference and reconciliation that Kymilcak explores in this book have significant implications for the philosophy of multiculturalism. In this article, Kymilcka examines the symbiotic relationship between the politics of reconciliation and the politics of diversity, arguing that the former encourages the latter by fostering multicultural notions of citizenship.

Modood writes that cultural racism, Islamophobia, and an unforeseen challenge to secular modernity have further muddled what started as a story of racial exclusion and the black-white divide in his 2005 book *Multicultural Politics: Racism, Ethnicity, and Muslims in Britain*. Having realized that the problems of South Asians are at the core of so-called "race relations" in Britain, Tariq Masood has established a novel and powerful viewpoint. This book brings together some of his most important social, political, and theoretical insights, as well as a new Introduction and Conclusion, giving the reader access to a unique perspective on the relationship between religion and race [13].

Considering the rise of Muslim political assertiveness and responses to it in the context of rethinking multiculturalism and Britishness, Modood has released *Still Not Easy Being British: Struggles for a Multicultural Citizenship* (2010). There has never been a more opportune moment for the thoughtful contemplation and courageous engagement in debates that characterize Modood's work and have made him a recognized intellectual commentator on Muslim politics and diversity.

If you are interested in studying Indian Literature via the lens of multiculturalism, I highly recommend Ashok Chaskar's *Multiculturalism in Indian Fiction in English* (2010) [15]. There are six chapters in the book. The fundamental concepts of multiculturalism are laid forth in the first chapter. Chaskar mulls over multiculturalism and emphasizes the term's breadth and depth across disciplines such as politics, sociology, anthropology, and literary studies. According to him, multiculturalism as a social philosophy unites disparate ideas like tolerance for and appreciation of other cultures, openness to new experiences and perspectives, and the harmonious coexistence of all ethnicities. In addition, he provides examples of multiculturalism's critical theory and its application to Indian literature. As the book progresses, Chaskar makes an effort to examine Indian novels written in English in the context of multiculturalism. He examines the works of Mulk Raj Anand (1935), Khushwant Singh (1956), Anita Desai (1971), and Arundhati Roy (1997), among other renowned Indian authors, in the context of multiculturalism. In a nutshell, this anthology sets out to use literature to demonstrate how the social theory of multiculturalism promotes harmonious communities by encouraging its readers to appreciate and learn from one another's cultural backgrounds and practices.

Just recently, in 2016, M. Rajagopalachary and K. Damodar Rao produced a book titled *Multiculturalism in Indian Tradition and Literature* (2016). It is a compilation of analytical

articles written by academics from various South Indian institutions. Culture, hybridity, colonialism, harmony, humanism, pluralism, diversity, Dalit literature, Bhakti literature, Nativism, etc., are only a few of the topics explored in these writings. Chapters 15, 19, 21, 22, and 23 include studies that examine literary literature through the lens of diversity. Multiculturalism is discussed in these chapters through the lens of works by U. R. Anantha Murthy (1973), Bharathipura, Salman Rushdie (1995), *The Moor's Last Sigh*, Khushwant Singh (2005) *Death at My Doorstep*, Rohinton Mistry (1991) *Such a Long Journey*, and Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni (1997) *The Mistress of Spies* [16].

A Study of Multiculturalism in Mordecai Richler's Novels is the title of Janardan Kamble's 2013 thesis at Shivaji University, Kolhapur. Mordecai Richler, a significant character in Canadian literature, is examined in terms of how his works represent diversity. The novels of Canadian author Richler are the focus of this study; they represent multicultural communities in Montreal, Quebec, and elsewhere in Canada. The peace and understanding between different groups that enrich Richler's writing is a central topic of this study.

In 2010, Kalika S. Shah presented her dissertation titled "Multiculturalism and the Politics of Identity: A study of the Novels of Bapsi Sidhwa, Rohinton Mistry, and Boman Desai" at Veer Narmad South Gujarat University in Surat. Specifically, her dissertation will examine the works of Bapsi Sidhwa, Rohinton Mistry, and Boman Desai, three Indian-born expatriate Parsee authors. These South Asian-born Parsee authors immigrated to North America in the second part of the twentieth century. From a multiethnic perspective, their works provide a number of options. These Parsee authors in exile use both an insider's perspective on their home country and a foreigner's perspective on their new home to explore the issue of migration, relocation, and identity shifts in their work. These books show how, in response to shifting global environments, both individual and group identities are established and reinterpreted.

IV. CONCLUSION

Great literature is born from a language that has its foundation in the accumulated wisdom of generations. The banyan tree of Indian languages was grafted with the English language. The language has not yet established deep roots, so the grafting was only partially successful. Its literature, as a result, has to make do with a tiny audience and a minimal social context in which to function. As a result, Multiculturalism has not provided an environment conducive to its maintenance and development. After discussing the unique cultural pressures exerted on Indian English literature, it is essential to emphasize that its potential is best realized within the marga tradition, as India's national literature, and not as the literature of a particular region within the desi tradition. However, it is currently India's only form of national literature, so it is here to stay, like it or not. Furthermore, it is the only medium available for portraying the marga side of contemporary Indian life. Realizing this role and swiftly shedding its multicultural setting is crucial to the country's development.

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